

RESEARCHES CONCERNING THE INSERTION OF THE STUDENTS AND GRADUATES FROM THE FIELD OF "ENGINEERING" THROUGH THE JOB FAIR

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Abstract

Purpose – To find out if there is a demand from the local companies for the labor force with higher education from the "Engineering" field and to improve the insertion on the labor market of the students through the event necessary for the research to take place.

Methodology/approach – The research was conducted through one of the events from the project, with the help of the survey which was used as a method and two categories of questionnaires that were created as tools: one for students/graduates and another for companies' representatives participating in the event.

Findings – All the companies participating in the event showed their availability for hiring labor force with higher education from the "Engineering" field and a great number of the students and graduates showed their interested in this regard.

Research limitations/implications – The results of the research reflect in the best way the local situation, but this can vary from one branch to another within the university given that these are in different regions of the country.

Practical implications – The implementation of the recommendations resulting from the research would be extremely useful both for students and university and for local companies looking for labor force with higher education.

Originality/value – The research is innovative due to the fact that it was done for the first time within the TUC-N branch from Satu Mare (including the Job fair inside the branch necessary for the research to take place).

Key words: "Engineering" field, higher education, insertion of students.

Introduction

Employability plays an important role in the Bologna Process, higher education having the task to develop the students' skills and abilities in line with the market needs that lead to their easier integration into the labor market (<http://www.anosr.ro/profesional/angajabilitate/>).

According to a study conducted by UNICEF in 2014, "high school graduates earn with 25 percent – 31 percent more than those who have completed primary and lower secondary education" while "the earnings obtained by university graduates outnumber the earnings of those who drop out of school after high school with almost 67 percent"(Crisbășanu, S.D., 2016).

Regarding the time needed to find the first job of the graduates according to the level of education and field, registered until 2011, the graduates of Engineering Sciences are in the fourth position from 13 fields, with a period of time of approximately 3 and a half months, the first three positions being occupied in the following order by the graduates of Architecture and Urbanism, Economic Sciences and Social and Political Sciences (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Time required for hiring after graduation depending on the field (expressed in months)

Source: (Pantazi, R., 2011)

Most hiring offers are for the graduates of Humanities, followed by Economic sciences and Engineering Sciences (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of offers that graduates had when hiring depending on the field

Domain	One offer	More offers
Humanities	59%	41%
Economic sciences	63%	37%
Engineering sciences	64%	36%
Natural sciences	68%	32%
Physical education and sport	68%	32%
Law	69%	31%
Social and political sciences	69%	31%
Veterinary medicine	69%	31%
Health	69%	31%
Exact sciences	72%	28%
Agricultural and forestry sciences	76%	24%
Architecture and urbanism	78%	22%
Arts	82%	18%

Source: (Florea, R., 2011)

The percentage of 36 percent can be justified by the fact that Engineering sciences is a broad field, which consists of several different specializations (civil engineering, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, etc.), which is why the possible careers for the graduates from engineering are wide and varied(<https://www.infomunca.ro/vizualizeaza-articol/Ce-poti-face-cu-o-diploma-de-inginer-210>).

Perhaps because of this, only about 56 percent of the graduates from Engineering sciences work in the specialization they graduated. This phenomenon is not only found in Romania, it is estimated that "40

percent of the engineers with diploma from all over the world choose managerial positions, although technical careers still offer them interesting perspectives" (Vidroiu, A., 2008).

Among the methods used by the graduates for hiring are: applying for a vacant job (71 percent), calling to personal contacts (parents, relatives, friends) (25 percent), appealing to the Labor Force Agency (22 percent), direct contact with the company regardless of the existence of the job offer (13 percent), appealing to human resources agencies (9 percent), hiring during studies (8 percent) and job search by announcement (3 percent) (Pantazi, R., 2011).

According to a survey of 5,000 top companies from 20 countries realized by the French consulting group RH Emerging and the German institute Trendence, 45 percent of the international companies believe that faculty remains an important selection criterion and "only a third looks strictly to the skills and experience of the candidate" (<https://www.hipo.ro/locuri-de-munca/vizualizare-Articol/1126/Principalele-facultati-din-Romania-care-te-ajuta-la-angajare>).

If we only report to the Romanian market, 18 percent of the employers believe that "graduates need to resume the things they should have learned in faculty, and 43 percent think that new employees need to learn additionally to cope with the received job" (Florea, R., 2011).

For this reason, for some employers, partnerships with technical universities, internships or trainings are necessary, as existing programs offered by universities do not fully correspond to the multitude of jobs that they bring for hiring (Mirea, C., 2012).

At the level of 2016 at the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, one of the major universities in Cluj, where more than 20,000 students study, graduated more than 2,000 of them (<https://www.utcluj.ro/studenti/festivitatea-absolventilor/2016/>).

According to the university statistics, "77 percent of the graduates are employed in the first year after completing their studies, of which 65 percent are in the job from the qualification domain" (Avram, S., 2016).

Results of the research

In the light of the answers given by the participants in the Job fair, it is clear that the best ways to promote the event among young people is through "chief of the year from the specialization" (62.5 percent) and the "event announcement" (37.5 percent) through the posters within the faculty. This question had four answer variants, one or more of which could have been chosen (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Participants questionnaire (students and graduates) - How did you find out about the organization of this event?

91.7 percent of the participants consider that the organized event was useful in a high, very high or extremely high extent, while more than half (53.3 percent) of the representatives of the companies are of the same opinion (Figure 3).

Figure 3. How do you assess the extent to which the event was useful to you?

Also, all participants in the event (100 percent) and 93.3 percent of the company representatives were satisfied with the organization of the event, its organization being appreciated as good, very good or excellent (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Please rate the organization of this event:

The fact that the most important companies from the region participated in the event is also confirmed by the participants' replies, no less than 95.8 percent of them appreciated that the participation of the companies (both in number and as a job offer) was good, very good or excellent (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Participants questionnaire (students and graduates) - How do you assess the participation of companies (as number and job offer) in this event?

60 percent of the companies' representatives described the presence of the participants in the event as good or very good, both in number and as interest showed (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Company representatives' questionnaire - How do you assess the participation of students and graduates (in number and as interest showed) in this event?

Companies that attended the Job fair came up with offers for "jobs for students and graduates" (100 percent) and offers for "summer practice for students" (80 percent). This question had three answer variants, one or more of which could have been chosen (Figure 7).

V1 = jobs for students and graduates;
 V2 = summer practice for students;
 V3 = other offers:

Figure 7. Company representatives' questionnaire - With what offers did you participate in this event?

From the jobs offered by the companies, most of them were addressed to the participants from "machine building technology" (80 percent), followed by "industrial economic engineering" (40 percent) and "automation and applied informatics" (40 percent). This question had seven answer variants, one or more of which could have been chosen (Figure 8).

V1 = machine building technology;
 V2 = industrial economic engineering (management, quality, logistics etc.);
 V3 = automation and applied informatics;
 V4 = computers;
 V5 = electronics and telecommunication;
 V6 = electrical engineering;
 V7 = other: "human resources".

Figure 8. Company representatives' questionnaire - In which domain(s) fit the jobs from the offer of the company that you represent?

The Job fair has been a real success, given the large number of participants, participating companies and the number of CVs submitted: 6.7 percent of the companies received more than 10 CVs, 13.3 percent between 5 and 10 CVs and almost half of the companies (46.7 percent) received under 5 CVs (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Company representatives' questionnaire - How many CVs did you receive from the participants in this event?

86.7 percent of the companies participating in the Job fair believe that university must be involved very much, and the rest (13.3 percent) that university must be involved much in the economic and/or social issues of the region (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Company representatives' questionnaire - How much should the university involve in the economic and/or social issues of the region?

All the participating companies (100 percent) expressed their interest in maintaining the collaboration with the Satu Mare Branch of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Company representatives' questionnaire - Is the company you represent interested in maintaining the collaboration with the Satu Mare Branch of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca?

Conclusions and recommendations

According to the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The best ways to promote the event among the young people from the technical higher education are through "chief of the year from the specialization" (62.5 percent) who can transmit the information directly to the interested ones, usually via Facebook, Yahoo Groups, etc. and through the "event announcement" (37.5 percent) placed as posters within the faculty;
- The statement from the beginning of the research, "only about 56 percent of the graduates from Engineering sciences work in the specialization they graduated" is confirmed given the diversity of the job offers brought by the companies participating in the Job fair compared to the number of specializations existing for the bachelor's degree at the Satu Mare Branch of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca;
- 95.8 percent of the participants in the Job fair appreciated that participation of the companies (both in number and as a job offer) was good, very good or excellent and 60 percent of the companies' representatives described the presence of the participants in the event as good or very good, both in number and as interest;
- The Job fair was a real success, 91.7 percent of the participants and more than half of the representatives of the companies (53.3 percent) consider that the organized event was useful in a high, very high or extremely high extent;
- The companies participating in the event showed their availability for both hiring and practice, offering "jobs for students and graduates" (100 percent) and "summer practice for students" (80 percent);
- The event aimed to improve the insertion on the labor market of the students and graduates from the field of "Engineering" and considering the number of CVs submitted it can be considered that the aim has been achieved: 6.7 percent of the companies received more than 10 CVs, 13.3 percent between 5 and 10 CVs and almost half of the companies (46.7 percent) received under 5 CVs;
- 86.7 percent of the companies participating in the Job fair believe that university must be involved very much, and the rest (13.3 percent) that university must be involved much in the economic and/or social issues of the region and they expressed their interest in maintaining the collaboration with the Satu Mare Branch of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca.

The recommendations that can be made following the results obtained are:

- To organize other Job fair editions in the future in order to help students/graduates and companies, and thus to facilitate the increase of the youth insertion in the labor market;
- To organize other common actions with the business environment to improve the relationships aimed to receive students in companies to acquire skills and gaining the required experience needed for hiring after graduation (diploma themes involving the student in research, summer practice, part-time hiring, etc.).

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